

Electrochemical Oxidation of cYclic and biogenic substrates
for high efficiency production of organic CHEMICALS

The Concept

ELOXYCHEM is a Horizon Europe project focused on replacing conventional chemicals processes through a novel electrochemical conversion platform and drop-in technology, leveraging renewable industrial feedstocks and waste streams from traditional thermochemical chemicals production.

Goals

- Reduce by 30%** energy use in energy intensive processes
- Support EU independence** from fossil fuels
- Enable techno-economic feasibility** of new technologies and processes
- Empower the potential** of renewable energies

Combine the electrochemical oxidation processes (EOPs) advantages with the opportunities of AI-based digital technologies

Latest Progress

- Validation of electrochemical processes compatible with **renewable energy** integration and variable power loads
- Reduction potential** identified for greenhouse gas emissions, energy use, and chemical waste compared to conventional routes
- Initial **social and environmental impact** assessments confirming the sustainability potential of the technology

Project Partners

